

NEW AND EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract: In this article, you can find several modern and effective ways for teaching English to elementary school students and this methods presented in this article will help children learn English quickly and effectively. Every teacher faces challenges when teaching elementary grades, and the techniques in this and other articles can be of great help in overcoming them, because different exercises and games are more interesting for children than lessons

Key words: Teaching lessons through song, Total physical response(TPR), Creative expression, Theatricalization and dramatization, Using multimedia, Time and space, The silent way.

Introduction. Young children's brains are like white paper and they absorb information quickly. However, teaching them something requires a lot of patience and creativity. Especially, teaching foreign languages is a very responsible task.

Memorizing new words can be an effective method for adults, but getting first graders to sit up straight is very difficult. So you should use funny methods during the lessons. In the beginning, you may face several troubles , but you can feel advantages after some lessons.

This article shows some effective methods to teach English to young children.

Teaching lessons through song

Every English learners know at least one song in English, for example ABC or Happy birthday song. Teaching vocabulary and grammar to young children through music is a fun and effective way. If you do not know song about any theme, you can find from You Tube or Twinkle litter star sites.

Total physical response (TPR)

Second method is the Total physical response. In this method, teachers and pupils communicate with facial expressions and gestures. This is very popular approach to lessons, for example young children can show the word happy through their faces.

Also TPR is usually used in online lessons. Children may tired of sitting long times and this method helps to regain energy and focuses considerate.

Creative expressions

Next is Creative expression. Teaching children language by using art and drawings is also beneficial. Such as ,pupils may draw a sun and tell the word in English. This is very memorable way.

Theatricalization and dramatization

Movies,tales and cartoons in English is favourite method for teachers and favourite exercise for pupils. Because pupils memorize princes and princesses with English words and phrases

Using multimedia

Using multimedia gives great chance for children. It helps to grow the interest of children and pay attention for a long time. By using this method,we can improve pupil's language skills. For example, our topic is Animals,if we show animal's picture and listen their voice by TV or computer, they can learn easily the names of the animal.

Time and space

Every pupil has no equal learning abilities. Some children understand quickly and completely, but others may face some difficulties to learn topics. At that time, good teacher should give extra time and information to the students. Teacher should give enough time for practice and should explain their mistakes .

The silent way

The silent way is a language teaching method created by Cael Gattegno that makes huge use of silence as a teaching method. In this method, teacher and pupils change their positions during the lesson. Teacher don't teach , speak only monitor the process.

Conclusion. In teaching English to elementary school pupils, these methods help all teachers. However, these methods may have various advantages and disadvantages. How useful these methods are in the course of the lesson is also related to the relationship between the teacher and the student and the effective use of these methods also depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills. In conclusion, effective methods of teaching English do not end with the methods in this article. In addition, you can combine several methods to create new and effective methods.

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